

Screening Results :

The results of the antibacterial screening of the seven synthesised compounds are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—*N*-ARYL-*N'*-2-(4-METHYLPHENYL)-THIAZOLYL-*N''*-ALKYL (OR H) GUANIDINES

Sl. No.	Alkyl group	Bacteria	
		<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>E. coli</i>
(Concentration—1000 ppm)			
Aryl group=Phenyl			
1.	H	+	+
2.	Ethyl	+	+
3.	<i>n</i> -Butyl	-	+
Aryl group= <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl			
4.	H	-	+
5.	Methyl	+	+
6.	Ethyl	-	+
7.	<i>n</i> -Propyl	+	+

(+) Growth ; (-) No growth.

The test organisms were *B. subtilis*, a bacteria from Gram-positive group and *E. coli*, a bacteria from Gram-negative group and the concentration used was 1000 ppm. From the results it can be inferred that the thiazolyl guanidines are more active against Gram-positive bacteria than the Gram-negative one.

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Search for New Hypoglycemic Agents-Part IV N¹-(Arylideneamino)-N³-(Arylsulphonamido) Guanidines

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A series of N¹-(arylideneamino)-N³-(arylsulphonamido)-guanidines has been synthesised. Three of these compounds when screened on rats at an oral dose of 250 mg/kg reduced the blood sugar up to 9%.

It has been reported that several guanidines¹⁻⁴ possess significant hypoglycemic activity. Some arylsulphonamides⁵⁻⁷ are also known to exhibit marked antidiabetic property. It seemed, therefore, of interest to synthesise the title compounds with the object to ascertain whether the presence of arylsulphonamido moiety in guanidines could augment their hypoglycemic potency.

N¹-(Arylidene) thiosemicarbazide was refluxed with methyl iodide in ethanol for 2 hr. to give the hydroiodide of N¹-(arylidene)-S-methyl thiosemicarbazide. The latter was treated with aqueous 2N-Na₂CO₃ solution to yield N¹-(arylidene)-S-methyl thiosemicarbazide which on being refluxed with various aryl sulphonyl hydrazines in ethanol for 48 hr furnished N¹-(arylideneamino)-N³-(arylsulphonamido) guanidines.

Experimental

Melting points are not corrected. I. R. spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer 577 in KBr pellets.

N¹-(Arylidene) thiosemicarbazides : were prepared according to the method of Jack et al⁸.

N¹-(Arylidene)-S-methyl thiosemicarbazides :

A mixture of N¹-(arylidene) thiosemicarbazide (.05 mole) and methyl iodide (.05 mole) in ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into ice cold water and filtered. The filtrate consisting of the HI-salt of N¹-(arylidene)-S-methyl thiosemicarbazide was neutralized with aqueous 2N-Na₂CO₃ solution to give the precipitate of N¹-(arylidene)-S-methyl thiosemicarbazide which was recrystallized from ethanol.

The properties and analytical data of the compounds thus obtained are summarized in Table 1.

*For correspondence.

NOTES

TABLE 1
Ar-CH=N.NH.OS.CH,
||
NH

Sl. No.	Ar	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Nitrogen%	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	C ₆ H ₅	54	50	C ₉ H ₁₁ N ₂ S	21.98	21.76
2.	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	97	55	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ OS	19.13	18.83
3.*	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	81	55	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ S	19.89	20.29
4.	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	99	60	C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₂ SCl	18.68	18.46
5.*	2,4-(Cl) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	109	58	C ₉ H ₉ N ₂ SCl ₂	16.52	16.03
6.	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	169	50	C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	23.15	23.53
7.	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	86	48	C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	23.94	23.53
8.	4-(CH ₃) ₂ NC ₆ H ₃	137	52	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ S	24.10	23.73
9.*	3-OCH ₃ -4-OHC ₆ H ₃	85	65	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	17.29	17.57
10.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	159	68	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	17.15	16.60

* Analysed satisfactorily for sulphur.

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	Ar	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Nitrogen%	
						Found	Calcd.
1.	C ₆ H ₅	OCH ₃	280	60	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	20.49	20.18
2.	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	225	65	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	21.86	21.15
3.	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	H	139	55	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	20.52	20.18
4.	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	NHCOCH ₃	179	58	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	21.18	20.79
5.	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	OCH ₃	158	68	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	18.36	18.57
6.*	4-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	175	62	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	19.81	19.39
7.	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	206	70	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	20.55	20.29
8.	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	H	196	52	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ SCl	19.48	19.92
9.	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	NHCOCH ₃	259	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ SCl	20.79	20.56
10.*	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	OCH ₃	218	48	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ SCl	18.66	18.35
11.*	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	209	70	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ SCl	18.77	19.15
12.	2,4-(Cl) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	CH ₃	195	60	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ SCl ₂	17.16	17.50
13.	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	228	65	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S	22.77	22.34
14.	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	H	209	55	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	23.55	23.20
15.	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	NHCOCH ₃	231	58	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	22.93	23.39
16.	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	OCH ₃	230	68	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	21.91	21.43
17.	(CH ₃) ₂ NC ₆ H ₃	OCH ₃	158	62	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	21.20	21.54
18.	(CH ₃) ₂ NC ₆ H ₃	CH ₃	193	70	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	22.92	22.46
19.	3-CH ₃ O-4-OHC ₆ H ₃	OCH ₃	270	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	17.34	17.81
20.	3-CH ₃ O-4-OHC ₆ H ₃	CH ₃	196	48	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	18.18	18.56
21.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	NHCOCH ₃	204	70	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	19.58	19.35
22.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	OCH ₃	275	65	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	17.59	17.19
23.	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	CH ₃	220	60	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	17.48	17.90

* Screened for hypoglycemic activity.

*N*¹-(Arylideneamino)-*N*⁸-(aryl sulphonamido) guanidines :

*N*¹-(Arylidene)-*S*-methyl thiosemicarbazide (0.25 mole) was refluxed with an appropriate aryl sulphonyl hydrazine in ethanol for 48 hr. The solid obtained on cooling was recrystallized from ethanol.

The compounds thus prepared (Table 2) showed I. R. spectral bands at 1620-1660 cm⁻¹ (-C=N-), 1160-1190 cm⁻¹ (Sec SO₂NH-) and 3100-3400 cm⁻¹ (-NH).

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Chemical Investigation of *Tectona grandis* (roots)

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TECTONA *grandis* (Verbenaceae) commonly grows in India, Burma, Thailand, China and East Indies. Its remarkable resistance to termites makes it the most valuable wood for every type of construction. Chemical examinations of the leaves¹, wood² and roots³ have been carried out earlier. The present chemical investigation of the roots revealed the presence of eight compounds (A-H) i.e., 1-hydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone, tectoquinone, pachybasin, dehydrotectol, tectol, β -sitosterol, obtusifolin and betulinic acid out of which four compounds viz. tectoquinone, tectol, dehydrotectol and β -sitosterol have been reported earlier from the roots³. Obtusifolin is reported for the first time in this genus.

Experimental

The roots used in this investigation were procured from Kerala. The air dried roots powder (3.5 Kg) was extracted with hot acetone and alcohol respectively. The acetone extract was chromatographed on silicagel. Elution of the column with different solvents and their mixtures yielded compounds (A-H). No compound could be isolated from the alcohol extract.

Compound A (1-hydroxy-2-methyl anthraquinone) :

Petroleum ether-benzene (9 : 1). It crystallised from petroleum ether as yellow needles (35 mg), m.p. 183-84° and answered sodium dithionite colour test for quinones. Methyl ether m.p. 156°. It was found to be identical with an authentic sample of 1-hydroxy-2-methyl anthraquinone (m.m.p., Co-TLC and IR Spectra).

Compound B (tectoquinone) :

Petroleum ether-benzene (8 : 2). It crystallised from methanol as light yellow needles (1.50 g), m.p. 178°. It was identified as tectoquinone by m.m.p., Co-TLC, superposable IR, NMR and MS.

Compound C (pachybasin) :

Petroleum ether-benzene (8 : 2). It crystallised from petroleum ether as yellow needles (100 mg), m.p. 175°. It gave brown colour with alcoholic FeCl₃ and was insoluble in Na₂CO₃ solution. Methyl ether m.p. 188-89°, acetate m.p. 179-81°. The IR, NMR, UV and MS were found to be identical with that of pachybasin⁴.

Compound D (dehydrotectol) :

Petroleum ether-benzene (7 : 3). It crystallised from petroleum ether as blue-green needles (450 mg), m.p. 196-97°. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 270 and 340 nm. It was identified as dehydrotectol by direct comparison with an authentic sample of dehydrotectol (Co-TLC, m.m.p. and superimposable IR spectra).

Compound E (tectol) :

Petroleum ether-benzene (4 : 8). It crystallised from methanol as colourless needles (1g), m.p. 216-18° and gave brown colour with alcoholic FeCl₃. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 275, 345 and 362 nm. Methyl ether 217-19°, acetate 197-99°. Its identity was confirmed as tectol by m.m.p., Co-TLC and superimposable IR.

Compound F (β -sitosterol) :

Compound F (150 mg) has been identified as β -sitosterol by direct comparison with an authentic sample (m.m.p., Co-TLC and superimposable IR).

Compound G (obtusifolin) :

Benzene-ethyl acetate (98 : 2). It crystallised from methanol as yellow needles (60 mg), m.p. 235-37°. It gave brown colour with alcoholic FeCl₃ and was soluble in aqueous Na₂CO₃ solution. $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 275 and 405 nm. Methyl ether m.p. 143-44°. Compound G was found to be identical with an authentic sample of obtusifolin (Co-TLC, m.m.p. and superimposable IR).

Compound H (betulinic acid) :

Compound H (1.0-g) has been identified as betulinic acid by direct comparison with an authentic sample (Co-TLC, m.m.p. and IR Spectra).